

EXPRESSION OF PAIN, SUFFERING AND EXPERIENCES IN USMON NOSIR 'S LYRICS

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Real poets will always be symbols of their country. They are like the rivers of their land, the clouds of their sky, to peaks close to each other, the caravans of their roads, and the babies of their mothers. At the same time, real poets are like the heart of their nation. Heine was the soul of his people. Pushkin is the heart of his people. Byron is the heart of his people. Finding these souls is equal to finding the foundations of life of these peoples. It is no exaggeration to say that Usmon Nosir is the heart of his people according to the scale of his words and experiences. He was literally on his way to becoming a national icon.

The more people talk and write about the poet, the less his works are analyzed and understood. Until today, we have read and studied the articles and memoirs of a number of literary scholars, writers and poets about Usman Nasir. In particular, "The voice of fate" by the well-known literary scholar Ibrahim Gafurov (Khurshid Davron site), Hero of Uzbekistan A. Oripov, A word about Usman Nasir, Literature and Art of Uzbekistan, 1983, Mirvaliyev, R. Shokirova. Uzbek writers. - Tashkent, Literary and Art Publishing House named after Gafur Ghulam, 2016. The article "Don't forget my garden" by researcher Diyora Sanayeva is one of them.

Usmon Nosir loves his country without hesitation. As a country, as a people, he prepared himself for any tests. Radiating from within is a very rare phenomenon. Few of humanity's children are lucky. I can observe the radiating of the word from the inside as a miracle in Boboraqim Mashrab, Mirzo Ghalib, Geyne, Lorca, Cholpan, Usmon Nosir. Usmon Nosir's poems and epics are surrounded by clouds, and the moon shines brighter from the clouds and makes emotional hearts go wild. The moon, the wind, the clouds - the clouds that create beauty and life give charm to Usmon Nosir 's poems.¹ "Who do we mean when we say Usmon Nosir?" He has such a talent that he is a fire that burns wherever he touches. Looking at the short life of the poet, one is sure to have long thoughts. Because in this lightning-like life, you see and feel that many opportunities have burned out. Usmon Nosir is the dew that has not yet flowed from the mother of the great and eternal poetry, it is a semi-smile that is frozen forever on our lips without turning into laughter. "His poems are alive, alive,

¹<https://kh-davron.uz/yangiliklar/muborak-kin/ibrahim-gafurov-usman-nasir>.

untethered pieces of life," the hero of Uzbekistan, poet Abdulla Oripov, was absolutely right.²

However, he was a male poet. His poems were written on the Uzbek soil, his dark hair was stubbornly curled and the licks of fame were flying over his fiery head. Despite being so young, he was sent to Russia, Armenia, and Tajikistan to read poetry at literary conferences as the most talented representative of Uzbek poetry.

Usmon Nosir's passionate heart went to the vastness, saw the lands and was filled with impressions. Even as a child, he was thirsty for impressions. He hastened to transfer the images of the universe to his rebellious heart. Living in new impressions gave him great pleasure.

He could not look at anything indifferently, and he could not pass by anything carelessly and carelessly.

Usmon Nosir!.. This name became known to the reader at the end of the twenties. In the thirties, he became a poet whose works readers eagerly await. Now he was described as a "poet by nature", a "born poet". Usmon Nosir was 20 years old at that time. As they say, "a future child is known from the beginning", Usmon Nosir, like our famous figures, had many positive qualities from a very young age. He was extremely intelligent, perceptive, wide-eyed, very curious, attentive, eager for knowledge, and hardworking. That's why Usmon Nosir was known as a "born poet" with creative talent from a young age. Apart from the poetic nature of the young poet, this recognition was the result of his devotion to creativity, his attempt to know the secret of creativity, his learning and searching along the way.

The young poet who said, "I made friends with Geyne, I got help from Lermontov", along with the creative interpretation of the charming qualities of Russian and world poetry, tried to acquire the riches of Eastern literature and oral creativity... In all his poems and translations, ³kismet There are lines and clauses! Maybe destiny entered his heart very early. But the voice of fate began to be heard in his poems from the thirty-third year without stopping.

The last lines in "Heart":

turn into lightning,

Yaril! It's okay if I die !.. » I consider this to be the voice of fate. The poet went on to predict his own fate. Or remember the famous "Monologue". In this case, all grassy lines are the voice of fate. And especially: "*Perhaps, without finishing - My*

²<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/unutmas-meni-bog-im/viewer>

³<https://kh-davron.uz/kutubkhona/uzbek/memuarlar/usman-nosir-2>

life will end... " Apparently, "Nile and Rome" is also a fate from head to toe. " My lamp is burning... a heavy Thought like a wounded wing presses on. It's like a flood in my heart... " Usman Nasir's argument with Homer in this mysterious poem, fighting a tiger with a gladiator on the Roman stage, the people's enjoyment of this bloody scene, and finally, " Rome is death from the game The crazy theater that was waiting for him was also a prophecy of his fate.

The poet's poems are full of incomprehensible strange and mysterious images of prophecy. The fate of this great man can be seen from each of his lines:

Shut up!.. I made the setting sun on the horizon

look like Shart's severed head.

The dawns burned to pieces

Reminded of the crackling blood!

Usmon Nosir, who carved his bare chest and dipped it in blood in the terrible Siberian forests!

Many people know and memorize the poem of Usmon Nosir called "1870", which is strangely portant, full of melodic distortions. In this, some people will be impressed that Razin's head is likened to the red sun. Someone else is moved by the fact that in the poem the mother looks at the moon that never sets, her bosom is a white soft cloud. The image of the garden is not absent in this poem, the image of the mother is similar to the image of the garden. The moon gives them imaginary pictures. And the moonlight shines. All the images in one poem interact with each other and reinforce each other. The allusions and melodies in it are truly inspired.

Such phenomena are manifested only in geniuses like Navoi, Hafiz, Byron, Geyne through the naturalness of genius art.

In fact, these three words are not related to each other in any way. The lines and clauses in which they are used are different. However, since Usmon Nosir 's poetry is born from the power of naturalness, he achieves the harmony of all three things - the bright harmony of feelings, words and melodies.

The poet describes the hardships of raising a child for a mother:

And he does not give words to suffering.

This time he endured like a mountain -

concludes a paragraph. Then comes the last stanza of the poem. In the 1984 edition we read:

Oh... he didn't know who he gave birth to,
he was just happy as always.

That's all. Nothing seems to have changed. The poem continues naturally. There is no interruption in the flow of thought and the development of content. But here, an important art closely related to the beautiful art of Usmon Nosir has completely disappeared...

We will get hold of the first edition of "Mehrim". Let's see what it says:

This time he endured like a mountain –

- Yu... he didn't know who you gave birth to.

Summary

Yes, indeed, the poet is still alive today, as if he is walking among us. Already, his works are being published, his poems are being memorized, books and plays are being created about him, all of which once again proves how valid the above verses are. It would be an exaggeration to say that the novel "Usmon Nosir" by the talented poet Tora Mirza, the book "Usmon Nosir" by the young and sharp writer Jovlon Jovliyev, and the stage play of the same name have rediscovered him in the imagination of the young generation. Not also, it is necessary to include such works in school textbooks and through this form the feelings of pride and pride in the hearts of our dear children towards the past and our great ancestors, to create Usmon Nosir of today and the future, and at the same time also relevant.

Usmon Nosir's appearance in literature attracted everyone's attention. His entry into the field of creativity was like the entry of an unknown wrestler who attracted everyone with his unparalleled strength. Yes, he came to the field of creativity with a young and small body and carried a huge burden. "Usmon came into our poetry like a wind. Maybe like a storm! It came with such a storm and wave that it completely destroyed some poetic style and creativity. He was written as "Lermontov of Uzbek" in our country, and "Pushkin appeared in the East" in Moscow newspapers, says poet Turob Tola.

died on March 23, 1944 (March 9, according to the camp archive documents. Site description) at the age of 32 in the Far East (in a camp near the village of Suslovo in the Mariinsk district of the Kemerevo region (now the settlement of Pervomaysk). But, as the poet himself said, the Motherland, our people, literature did not forget him!

If I break off like a leaf,
don't forget me, my garden.

He respects my work,
builds a statue of flowers.

My poems will be heard,

even after a thousand years,
you will not forget me, my garden... ⁴
("My garden")

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2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/unutmas-meni-bog-im/viewer>
3. <https://kh-davron.uz/kutubkhona/uzbek/memuarlar/usman-nosir-2>
4. S. Kambarova "The poet does not die"

⁴ *Kh. Davran site*

